

**INFRARED VERSUS LIGHT SCATTERING TECHNIQUES TO MONITOR THE
GEL TO LIQUID CRYSTAL PHASE TRANSITION IN LIPID MEMBRANES**

short title: **Lipid membrane phase transition: IR vs. light scattering**

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keywords: FTIR spectroscopy, Infrared spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Brillouin spectroscopy, lipid phase behavior

1 **ABSTRACT**

2

3 In this study, Fourier transform infrared, Raman as well as Brillouin spectroscopy have been
4 used to study lipid phase behavior of hydrated as well as dried multilamellar L- α -
5 phosphatidylcholine assemblies, in order to compare limitations and potentials of the
6 different techniques. Dried lipid samples have been studied in the presence and absence of
7 trehalose, which is known to affect the phase behavior of these systems. The methylene C-H
8 stretching (2800-3000 cm^{-1}) region in IR and Raman spectra provided mutually consistent
9 information on the rearrangement of lipid acyl chains occurring at the lipid melting
10 temperature. IR spectra have a higher signal to noise ratio, thus permitting a more precise
11 evaluation of the melting temperature. In the hydrated lipid samples, the CH stretching region
12 in the Raman spectra is less affected by the contribution of water compared to that in the IR
13 spectra. Raman spectra are particularly suitable to simultaneously study both lipid and water
14 contributions allowing to distinguish ice from non-frozen water below 0 °C. Brillouin light
15 scattering was used to probe the collective dynamics, i.e. the propagation velocity and the
16 attenuation of longitudinal acoustic modes in the lipid samples. Lipid phase transitions are
17 evident from a change in the temperature behavior of the acoustic velocity. Moreover, a
18 strong relaxation process with a characteristic time of 14 ps was observed in the sample dried
19 without trehalose with a maximum in acoustic attenuation at about 45°C, which likely reflects
20 the rearrangement of acyl chains.

21

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1 INTRODUCTION

2

3 Cell membranes are composed of a complex mixture of phospholipids, cholesterol and
4 proteins. Phosphatidylcholine (PC) is the most abundant phospholipid in cell membranes.
5 Liposomes composed of one type of lipid or mixtures of lipids have been used to study
6 properties of biological membranes. Lamellar lipid assemblies undergo radical changes in
7 physical state over narrow temperature ranges at a characteristic phase transition temperature
8 [1]. Lipid phase transitions occur at specific temperatures for each lipid depending on head
9 group type, chain length, chain saturation, hydration, and thermal history. The bilayer below
10 the main phase transition temperature exists in a closely packed gel state, with the acyl chains
11 relatively immobilized in a tightly packed array. In the more fluid, liquid crystalline state,
12 there is relatively more conformational disorder [2]. Not only, temperature, but also the
13 hydration state of the lipid head groups, determines the lipid phase state. Dehydration may
14 cause membranes to undergo fluid to gel phase transitions [3-5].

15 Many techniques are available to study lipid phase behavior, including differential
16 scanning calorimetry (DSC), Raman and infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD),
17 NMR, fluorescence spectroscopy, and computer simulations. One major drawback of high
18 sensitivity methods such as fluorescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) is that there is a
19 need for labeling and that the influence of the probe on the structure and behavior of the
20 system must be considered. Vibrational spectroscopic methods such as Raman and infrared
21 spectroscopy do not require labeling and can be used to accommodate aqueous as well as dry
22 samples with minimal sample preparation. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) is widely used
23 to monitor lipid phase behavior during changes in temperature or during drying [5-7]. Lipid
24 phase behavior can be studied by monitoring the temperature dependence of the symmetric or
25 antisymmetric CH_2 stretching bands at 2850 cm^{-1} and 2920 cm^{-1} , respectively [8]. Raman

1 spectroscopy is not as widely used as FTIR to study lipid phase behavior, which is likely due
2 to the generally higher signal to noise ratio of infrared spectra compared to that of Raman
3 spectra. Raman spectroscopy is also based on measurements of molecular vibrations.
4 Changes in lipid membrane structure can be observed by monitoring relative Raman peak
5 intensities that represent intra-and intermolecular order, which, in turn, are indicators of lipid
6 phase changes. The methylene C-C stretching ($1030-1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the methylene C-H
7 stretching ($2800-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) regions are used as indicators of membrane order [9,10], but
8 phase changes can also be detected by observing peak shifts [11,12]. With a confocal-Raman
9 microscope, it is possible to optically trap individual liposomes so that Raman scattering is
10 collected from one liposome while minimizing contributions from the surrounding solution
11 [13]. Just like Raman scattering, Brillouin light scattering (BLS) describes the inelastic
12 scattering of light from vibrations of matter. However, while in Raman spectroscopy photons
13 are scattered by interaction with vibrational and rotational transitions in molecules, Brillouin
14 spectroscopy involves the scattering of photons from low-frequency (GHz) collective
15 acoustic modes, the acoustic phonons. BLS has been used for measuring the viscoelastic
16 behavior of a large variety of samples ranging from liquids [14] to polymeric [15] and
17 biological systems [16]. The elastic characterization of oriented lipid multibilayers has been
18 obtained by angle resolved BLS measurements [17,18]. The collective short wavelength
19 dynamics of lipid membranes has also been studied using inelastic neutron scattering. The
20 corresponding dispersion relation for the gel and the liquid phases of lipid bilayers provides
21 information on the phase transition and the respective phase coexistence [19].

22 In this study, FTIR, Raman and Brillouin spectroscopy are used to study the lipid
23 phase behavior of hydrated and dried multilamellar L- α -phosphatidylcholine assemblies and
24 its influence on localized and collective dynamics. The C-H stretching ($2800-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$)
25 regions in IR and Raman spectra are analyzed to monitor the change in packing of the acyl

1 chains occurring at the phase transition, and to identify similarities and differences between
2 the two spectroscopic techniques. Brillouin spectroscopy was used to measure the
3 propagation velocity and attenuation of longitudinal acoustic modes, giving information on
4 the evolution of the elastic properties coinciding with the phase change and the relaxation of
5 density fluctuation.

8 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

10 **Preparation of liposomes**

12 L- α -phosphatidylcholine (Egg, Chicken) dissolved in chloroform was purchased from
13 Avanti Polar Lipids. The chloroform of the 25 mg ml⁻¹ lipid solution was allowed to
14 evaporate in a fume hood. The solution was then placed in a desiccator where pressure was
15 reduced by a vacuum pump for at least 12 hours. The end result of this evaporation was a
16 lipid film cake. Hydration of this lipid film was accomplished by adding water to achieve a
17 lipid concentration of 40 mg ml⁻¹. The solution was then agitated, and the hydrated lipid
18 suspension underwent 3 freeze/thaw cycles by alternately placing the sample vial in liquid
19 nitrogen and in warm water. This procedure yields stacked multilamellar vesicles.

21 **Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

23 Infrared absorption measurements were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 100 Fourier
24 transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (Perkin Elmer, Norwalk, CT, USA), equipped with a
25 narrow band Mercury/Cadmium/Telluride liquid nitrogen cooled IR-detector. The optical

1 bench was continuously purged with dry air from an FTIR purge gas generator (Whatman,
2 Clifton, NJ, USA). The acquisition parameters were: 4 cm^{-1} resolution, 8 co-added
3 interferograms, 4000-900 cm^{-1} wavenumber range. Spectra analysis and display were carried
4 out using Perkin-Elmer software (Perkin-Elmer, Norwalk, CT, USA).

5 For FTIR analysis 10 μL of lipid solution was sandwiched between two CaF_2
6 windows. Dried samples were prepared by drying 10 μL of lipid solution on a CaF_2 window
7 for 3 h under a flow of dry air (less than 3% RH). Drying in the presence of trehalose was
8 done using lipid/trehalose mass ratios of 1/2. Dried samples were heated up to 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10
9 min prior to FTIR analysis samples to remove residual water.

10 A variable temperature FTIR sample holder with heater device (Harrick Scientific
11 Products, Pleasantville, NY, USA) together with a Linkam pump system using liquid
12 nitrogen as a coolant (Linkam Scientific Instruments, Tadworth, Surrey, UK) were used for
13 temperature-dependent FTIR measurements. The sample temperature was monitored using a
14 thermocouple that was located close to the sample.

15 The temperature dependence of the FTIR spectra was studied by cooling the sample
16 from 20 $^\circ\text{C}$ to temperatures as low as -50 $^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of approximately 1 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The
17 sample was subsequently heated with 1 $^\circ\text{C/min}$, while acquiring FTIR spectra every 30 s.
18 Membrane fluidity was monitored by observing the position of the CH_2 symmetric stretching
19 band at approximately 2850 cm^{-1} , as previously described [8]. Briefly, second derivatives of
20 the IR spectra were taken using a thirteen-point smoothing factor, the 2865 to 2835 cm^{-1}
21 region was selected and normalized, and the position of the symmetric CH_2 stretching
22 vibration absorbance band (νCH_2) was calculated by taking the average of the spectral
23 positions at 80% of the band height. The νCH_2 lipid band position was plotted versus the
24 sample temperature, and phase transition temperatures were determined from the maxima in

1 the first derivatives of the νCH_2 versus temperature plots. Averages \pm standard deviations
2 were calculated from 2-4 measurements.

3

4 **Raman Spectroscopy**

5

6 Raman spectra were obtained using a micro-Raman setup equipped with a $\lambda=514.5$
7 nm excitation of an Argon Ion laser (Coherent mod. Innova 90) at ca. 20 mW power. A back
8 scattering geometry was realized using the 50x long working distance objective of an
9 OLYMPUS microscope MOD BX40. The scattered radiation was analyzed by a single
10 monochromator Horiba Jobin-Yvon model TRIAX320, equipped with a charged coupled
11 device detector (Horiba – SPECTRUM ONE) cooled at -136°C with liquid nitrogen. Twenty
12 scans in the $500\text{-}4200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral range were accumulated within a 30s integration time
13 using a 5 cm^{-1} resolution.

14 The sample was deposited onto a silicon slide, covered by a coverslip glass, and
15 placed on a variable temperature holder (Linkam stage mod. FTIR600 with LNP95 cooling
16 module) to monitor the temperature dependence of the scattered light. Frequency calibration
17 was performed using the spectral lines of silicon. Each sample was cooled down to the lowest
18 temperature at $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ rate as described for FTIR measurements; Raman spectra were
19 recorded at selected temperature values during heating of the sample at $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

20

21 **Brillouin Light Spectroscopy**

22

23 Brillouin light scattering measurements were performed using a single-mode 532 nm
24 solid state laser operated at 75 mW power as excitation source and a 20 cm achromatic lens
25 to focus and collect light from backscattering of the sample. The sample was sandwiched

1 between an optically polished silicon substrate and a silica glass overlay. Temperature was
 2 controlled by the same Linkam stage used for Raman measurements. The scattered light was
 3 filtered by a Sandercock-type tandem-multipass Fabry-Perot interferometer [20], recorded
 4 and analyzed by a custom made MCA [21]. Inelastically scattered light by thermally
 5 activated acoustic modes propagating into the sample is shifted by $\omega = \pm v \cdot q$ with respect to
 6 the elastic light, where v is the velocity of the acoustic modes and $q = 2nk_i$ is the momentum
 7 exchanged in the back scattering process, n is the refractive index of the sample and k_i the
 8 wavevector of the incident light. From this relation, it can be deduced that samples with
 9 longitudinal acoustic modes propagating at 2-3 km/s give rise to Brillouin peaks at about 10-
 10 20 GHz.

11 In case of light scattered by damped acoustic modes, a broadening of the Brillouin
 12 peaks can also be measured. In this case, the power spectrum of scattered light can be
 13 approximated by that of a damped harmonic oscillator (DHO) [22]:

$$14 \quad I(\omega) = \frac{I_0}{\rho} \times \frac{\omega_b^2 G_b}{(\omega^2 - \omega_b^2)^2 + \omega^2 G_b^2} \quad (1)$$

15 where ω_b and Γ_b approximately give the frequency position and linewidth (FWHM) of the
 16 Brillouin peaks. These parameters are related to the apparent longitudinal sound velocity, v_L ,
 17 and viscosity, η_L , through the relations $\omega_b = q v_L$ and $\Gamma_b = q^2 \eta_L / \rho$, where ρ is the mass
 18 density. The sound velocity, in turn, is related to the real part of the longitudinal modulus M'
 19 through the relationship $M' = \rho v_L^2$. It should be noted that the acoustic modes probed by BLS
 20 involve the cooperative motion of molecules with a wavelength of about 200 nm, propagating
 21 into the sample through a distance of at least a few wavelengths. BLS is thus sensitive to the
 22 collective dynamics of the system rather than to the localized molecular motions detected by
 23 IR and Raman spectroscopy.

24

1

2 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

3

4 Figure 1A shows IR spectra of lipids in the 3800-2600 cm^{-1} region. Overall, the IR
5 spectrum of the lipids in water is dominated by the signal from water. Water exhibits a strong
6 vibrational band at around 3300 cm^{-1} arising from OH stretching vibrations. The lipid bands
7 are visible on the shoulder of the water band, and become more pronounced in the dried
8 samples. The symmetric and antisymmetric CH_2 stretching vibrations arising from the lipid
9 acyl chains are visible at 2850 and 2920 cm^{-1} , respectively.

10 Figure 1B shows the Raman spectra of lipids obtained in the same wavenumber range
11 as the IR spectra. As expected, the intensity of the water signal is reduced with respect to
12 lipid bands compared to that in the IR spectrum. As a consequence, a resolved and complex
13 profile of CH stretching bands is visible in the spectrum of hydrated lipids. In both hydrated
14 and dried lipid samples the two main contributions in the 2700-3050 cm^{-1} spectral region can
15 be assigned to the symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibrational modes of the
16 methylene groups at around 2850 and 2880 cm^{-1} , respectively. The shoulder at 2928 cm^{-1} can
17 be assigned to a Fermi resonance of the symmetric methyl stretch and the band around 2970
18 cm^{-1} to the asymmetric methyl stretch of the acyl chains [23,24]. The lipid Raman bands of
19 the sample with trehalose are partially overlapped by the CH stretching bands of the sugar.
20 Fortunately, this overlap is negligible at 2850 cm^{-1} , so this band can be used to study lipid
21 phase behavior.

22 FTIR and Raman spectra of lipids during heating show shifts of bands in the
23 methylene stretching region associated with the gel to liquid-crystalline phase transition of
24 lipids (Figure 2). Both the symmetric and antisymmetric stretching bands shift to higher
25 wavenumber upon heating. In the Raman spectra, an increase in intensity of the band at 2850

1 with respect to the band at 2880 cm^{-1} can be observed, which reflects the increase of gauche
2 conformer fraction or the loss of lateral packing of the acyl chains occurring upon melting.
3 Moreover, the main transition is also seen in the $1000\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region of the Raman
4 spectrum (Figure 3). Bands in this region can be assigned to the C-C stretching motions of
5 all-trans (1130 and 1064 cm^{-1}) and gauche (1094 cm^{-1}) segments. A marked increase and red
6 shift of the 1094 cm^{-1} Raman band can be observed with increasing temperature, which likely
7 reflects the rearrangement of acyl chains and the increase in the number of gauche segments
8 coinciding with the melting process. Interestingly, Raman spectra can be used to reveal the
9 coexistence of frozen and non-frozen water below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 3B). The OH stretching
10 region of the lipid suspension at $T = -25^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows essentially the same contributions of pure
11 water except for an extra intensity at $3200\text{-}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which likely can be assigned to non-
12 freezable water molecules associated with the hydration layer [25,26].

13 Figure 4A shows the evolution of Brillouin spectra of a hydrated lipid sample in the
14 temperature range from -30 to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, showing a large variation in the peak position below 0
15 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. It should be noted that the variation at $T=0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is partially due to the formation of ice. On
16 the other hand, we emphasize that Brillouin peaks of longitudinal acoustic modes from ice
17 are expected at about 19 GHz in the back scattering geometry that was adopted here, [27],
18 which is out of our frequency window. This implies that the Brillouin peaks below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ arise
19 from the propagation of acoustic modes inside lipid domains that remain hydrated, separated
20 from pure ice domains. Below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ some residual water molecules that are not in the ice
21 crystals remain in a liquid-like state, strongly linked to the lipid molecules, as suggested by
22 the Raman spectra of Figure 3B.

23 The variation of the frequency position of BLS peaks between 0 and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ can
24 partially be attributed to the formation of ice thus inducing a change of the lipid

1 concentration. Conversely, the variation below -5 °C can be assigned to the characteristic
2 behavior of hydrated lipids below the melting temperature.

3 The BLS spectra of dried lipids show a smooth temperature evolution of the
4 characteristic frequency of the Brillouin peaks (Figure 4B). Due to the particular scattering
5 geometry that was chosen in the experimental set up, the peaks at about 5GHz are replica of
6 those at about 10 GHz, and they will not be considered in the following.

7 The BLS spectra of the dried lipid + trehalose sample are quite noisy due to the
8 intense elastic light scattering (Figure 4C). The signal of the acoustic phonons is clearly
9 visible, showing a smooth temperature evolution.

10 Figure 5 shows the band position of the symmetric CH₂ stretching band, derived from
11 the FTIR and Raman spectroscopy studies, as a function of temperature. The gel to the liquid-
12 crystalline phase transition coincides with a wave number shift from 2851 to 2853 cm⁻¹ in the
13 FTIR spectra of hydrated lipids, which is similar to the wavenumber shift observed in the
14 Raman data (from 2851.5 to 2853.5 cm⁻¹). Figure 5 shows that trehalose can prevent the
15 dehydration-induced increase in T_m of PC liposomes. Sugars are known to interact with lipids
16 in the dry state. By interacting with the polar headgroups of phospholipids, sugars depress T_m
17 of model membranes [28,29]. In order to deduce the T_m values from the FTIR and Raman
18 data, the gel to liquid-crystalline phase transition was described as a two state model. Within
19 this model, the band position at temperature T , P_T , can be expressed as [30]:

$$20 \quad P_T = \frac{P_G + m_G \cdot T + (P_L + m_L \cdot T) K_T}{1 + K_T} \quad (2)$$

21 where K_T is the equilibrium constant at temperature T between the two states, P_G and P_L are
22 the values of P_T at $T=0$ K in the gel and liquid state respectively, and m_G and m_L give their
23 temperature dependence, which is approximated as linear behavior in the analyzed region.

24 The equilibrium constant K_T can be expressed as a function of the melting temperature T_m
25 according to equation:

$$\ln(K_T) = C \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \quad (3)$$

where C is proportional to the melting enthalpy. A non-linear least squares method has been used to fit the experimental data in Fig. 5 with equations 2 and 3 and the obtained T_m values are reported in Table 1.

FTIR measurements indicate that hydrated liposomes have a T_m at approximately -7 °C. The T_m increases to 34 °C when liposomes are dried in the absence of trehalose, whereas in the presence of trehalose the T_m decreases to -21 °C, far below that of the hydrated control. Thus, the lipid bilayer remains in the liquid crystalline phase during dehydration at room temperature (22 °C). The T_m values derived from the Raman spectra closely resemble those of the FTIR spectra: T_m values were found to be -6, 29 and -27 °C for hydrated lipids, dried lipids, and lipids dried with trehalose. The slight differences in T_m values of the dried samples compared to those obtained from the FTIR spectra are likely due to small differences in water content. Small differences in water content have a great effect on T_m of dried lipids.

Figure 6A shows the frequency shift and Figure 6D the linewidth of BLS spectra of the hydrated lipid sample. The frequency shift displays a similar behavior compared to that of aligned multilamellar samples studied by BLS [31]. In the latter case the cusp-like temperature behavior of the longitudinal elastic modulus was assigned to the liquid-crystalline to gel phase transition of lipids. It should be noted that in the present study, the elastic properties averaged over different directions with respect to the acyl chains in a heterogeneous non-aligned multilamellar sample have been probed. This implies that despite the disordered nature of the samples the melting transition of the lipids can still be observed. On the other hand, the jump in the value of the frequency shift occurring between 0 and -5 °C can partially be attributed to the change in lipid concentration induced by ice formation. The linewidth (lower panel) stays almost constant in the ordered phase and decreases with increasing temperature in the disordered phase. This behavior is dominated by the water

1 viscosity as confirmed by the data of pure water deduced from previous BLS and ultrasonic
2 experiments [32,33] and reported for sake of comparison as a line in Fig. 6D.

3 Figure 6B shows the frequency shift and Figure 6E the linewidth of the BLS spectra
4 of dried lipids. The transition temperature corresponds to a smooth change in the temperature
5 dependence of the Brillouin frequency shift. The effect of the transition on the collective
6 properties (propagation of acoustic modes) is much less pronounced compared to that
7 observed in the hydrated lipids. In fact, the acoustic properties of the dried lipids are typical
8 of a viscoelastic fluid, affected by relaxation processes. The presence of a strong relaxation
9 active in the GHz frequency range is evident from the pronounced maximum in the acoustic
10 absorption, i.e. in the Brillouin linewidth, at about 45 °C. The characteristic time of this
11 relaxation process is given by $\tau = 1/\omega_b \approx 14$ ps at 45 °C. A dispersion in the velocity of the
12 acoustic modes associated with this absorption must be taken into account, i.e. a bending in
13 the temperature dependence of Brillouin frequency, which can partially mask the effect of the
14 melting transition of the lipid. Concerning the microscopic origin of this relaxation process, it
15 is interesting to note that a relaxation with similar characteristic times revealed by BLS in
16 polybutadiene has been attributed to conformational changes induced by thermally activated
17 rotations around $-\text{CH}_2\text{-CH=}$ bonds of the polymeric backbone [34,35]. In the same time
18 range a hypersonic relaxation process has been also observed in a simple liquid alkanol,
19 suggesting a coupling between hydrodynamic modes and the local molecular change of acyl
20 chain structure [36]. Similar conformational fluctuations are also present in lipid acyl chains
21 and the coupling of the associated density fluctuations with acoustic modes may be
22 responsible for the observed relaxation process.

23 Figure 6C shows the frequency shift and Figure 6F the linewidth of BLS spectra of
24 the dried lipid + trehalose sample. The signature of the melting transition in the temperature
25 dependence of the Brillouin frequency shift is more clearly visible compared to that of lipids

1 dried in the absence of trehalose. In this case no clear signatures of relaxation processes are
2 observed in the investigated temperature range, so that the change in the slope of ω_b can be
3 entirely assigned to the melting transition. The absence of strong relaxations and the higher
4 value of the sound velocity are both connected to the amorphous behavior of the sample. In
5 fact, the good glass-forming properties of trehalose are connected to its protective actions
6 during drying. Moreover, some water molecules are usually trapped between sugar and lipid
7 molecules. The very large value of the Brillouin linewidths may be due to the presence of
8 micrometric heterogeneities in the sample, which are also responsible for both the scattering
9 of phonons and the intense elastic scattering of photons giving rise to the huge elastic
10 contribution in the spectra.

11

12 **CONCLUSIONS**

13

14 Fourier transform infrared, Raman and Brillouin spectroscopy are complementary techniques
15 that can be used to study different aspects of lipid phase behavior of hydrated as well as dried
16 lipid systems. In particular, the methylene C-H stretching region in IR and Raman spectra can
17 be used to study the rearrangement of lipid acyl chains occurring at the lipid melting
18 temperature. IR spectra have a higher signal to noise ratio, thus permitting a more precise
19 evaluation of the melting temperature. In the hydrated lipid samples, the CH stretching region
20 in the Raman spectra is less affected by the contribution of water compared to that in the IR
21 spectra. Raman spectra are particularly suitable to simultaneously study both lipid and water
22 contributions allowing to distinguish ice from non-frozen water below the freezing point of
23 water.

24 The gel to liquid-crystalline phase transition coincides with an increase in wave number
25 position of the symmetric CH₂ stretching band in both FTIR and Raman spectra. Raman and

1 FTIR yield similar T_m values for hydrated as well as dried lipids. The phase transition
2 temperature, T_m , increases when liposomes are dried. When liposomes are dried in the
3 presence of trehalose, however, the T_m decreases compared to that of the hydrated control.
4 By interacting with the polar headgroups of phospholipids, trehalose can prevent the
5 dehydration-induced increase in T_m of PC liposomes.

6 The collective dynamics measured by BLS is rich of information on phase changes and on
7 the molecular rearrangement occurring in lipid membranes. Sound velocity in the hydrated
8 sample shows visible changes due to the partial freezing of water and to gel – liquid crystal
9 transition already observed in oriented lipid membranes. In the same sample the acoustic
10 attenuation in the disordered phase is dominated by viscosity of water. The dried sample with
11 trehalose shows solid-like properties, with a change to a more anharmonic behavior when
12 increasing temperature across the phase transition. In this case, the linewidth of Brillouin
13 lines is dominated by the heterogeneous nature of the sample rather than by acoustic
14 damping.

15 The relaxation of density fluctuations revealed by BLS in the disordered phase of the dried
16 sample without trehalose suggests the existence of a dynamic disorder, with conformational
17 changes occurring in the tens of picosecond time scale. The melting transition probed by
18 vibrational spectroscopies allows to better interpret this process supporting the rearrangement
19 of lipid chains in the liquid phase to be the molecular origin of this relaxation. Series of
20 measurements performed at different exchanged wave-vectors could help to obtain the
21 activation energy of this process and, together with molecular dynamics simulations, to
22 confirm its molecular origin.

23

24

1 **Acknowledgements:** Authors acknowledge the Centro Nazionale Trapianti for financial
2 support by the project “Crioconservazione di cellule per uso clinico umano, con particolare
3 riferimento ad alcune tipologie come le cellule staminali emopoietiche, mesenchimali e
4 cellule riproduttive”. S.C. acknowledges support from MIUR-PRIN (Project 2012J8X57P)
5 and PAT (Autonomous Province of Trento) “Grandi Progetti 2012” Project “MaDEleNA”
6 W.W. acknowledges support from the German Research Foundation (Deutsche
7 Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) via the Cluster of Excellence ‘From regenerative biology to
8 reconstructive therapy’ (REBIRTH) and grant WO-1735/6-1. H.O. acknowledges support
9 from the DFG via grant SI-1462/4-1.

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1 **Table 1.** T_m values deduced from FTIR and Raman data according to fit with Eqs. (2) and (3)

Technique\ T_m (°C)	Dried	hydrated	dried+trehalose
IR	33.9±2.0	-6.5±0.4	-21.4±1.2
Raman	29.4±2.5	-6.2±1.6	-26.6±2.0

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4

1 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

2

3 **Figure 1.** IR (1A) and Raman (1B) spectra of hydrated and dried multilamellar L- α -
4 phosphatidylcholine assemblies in the 3800-2600 cm^{-1} region.

5

6 **Figure 2.** IR (2A, 2B and 2C) and Raman (2D, 2E and 2F) spectra of the CH stretching
7 region of hydrated EPC (2A and 2D), dried EPC (2B and 2E) and dried EPC+trehalose
8 (EPC/trehalose: 1/2 weight ratio; 2C and 2F). The appropriate temperature ranges are
9 selected in order to follow the melting transition of EPC in each sample.

10

11 **Figure 3.** Raman spectra of hydrated PC lipids. Panel A: skeletal vibrations of EPC in
12 hydrated sample. Panel B: Raman spectra of the OH stretching region of pure H_2O (dashed
13 line) and of the hydrated lipid suspension (solid line) at $T = -25^\circ\text{C}$.

14

15 **Figure 4.** Brillouin spectra of hydrated EPC (4A), dried EPC (4B) and dried EPC+trehalose
16 (4C) at different temperatures. BLS spectra show the characteristic Brillouin doublets in the
17 GHz frequency range, due to the scattering of light from longitudinal acoustic modes
18 propagating into the sample.

19

20 **Figure 5.** Wavenumber position of the CH_2 symmetric stretching band of lipid acyl chains
21 obtained from IR (5A) and Raman (5B) spectra. A sigmoidal temperature behavior delimits
22 the melting transition. The continuous line is obtained by fitting the data with Eqs. 2 and 3.

23

24 **Figure 6.** Brillouin frequency shift ($\omega_b/2\pi$) and linewidth ($\Gamma/2\pi$) of hydrated EPC (6A and
25 6D), dried EPC (6B and 6E) and dried EPC+trehalose (6C and 6F) as a function of

1 temperature, obtained by a fitting procedure of BLS spectra with the DHO function of Eq.1,
2 convoluted with the instrumental resolution function. In figure 6B full line is referred to pure
3 water attenuation data.

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